

4 System Prototyping

This section presents the prototype of the new interface, developed in Figma, with modifications aimed at correcting the usability problems identified in the heuristic evaluation. For the creation of this new interface, the original project prototype was first obtained, which was updated to correspond to the interface present on the platform, in November 2025. In this version, the problem of the small photo in the news items had already been solved.

Next, the problems identified in the application's header and the adjustments made for the prototype will be presented. The font for language selection, which previously had low contrast with the dark blue background, was changed to white, facilitating visualization. Now, the header indicates, with white font, the page the user is on, helping them not to get lost in navigation. The header before the changes is present in Figure 1. Both solutions are presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Header before changes.

Fig. 2. Header updated according to heuristic evaluations.

The link "Organizações" (Organizations) was changed to the "Mais" (More) menu, which gathers and displays links to pages that were previously hidden by the old link, making navigation difficult. The terms present in the links, and consequently on the pages, were simplified for better user understanding. "Informes" changed to "Notícias" (News); "Iniciativas" changed to "Projetos" (Projects); "Recursos" became "Materiais" (Materials); "Formação" was modified to "Aprendizado" (Learning); "Organizações" was changed to "Instituições" (Institutions); and "Usuários" was updated to "Pessoas" (People). Changes present in Figure 3. Visual feedback was added to the "Entrar" (Log In) and "Criar conta" (Create Account) buttons, so that the user identifies that they are clickable buttons. The operation of the buttons before correction can be seen in Figure 4. The change can be seen in Figure 5.

On the login screen, the low contrast of the registration link was corrected, making it more visible to the user. The link for "Esqueceu a senha?" (Forgot

Fig. 3. Change from the old link "Organizações" to "Mais" and simplification of terms.

Fig. 4. Buttons without visual feedback.

Fig. 5. Visual feedback added when hovering over buttons.

password?) was also changed, changing its color to match the same dark blue of the registration link, maintaining a standard.

The "Entrar" (Log In) button was modified to be enabled only when the user fills in their information, which can be verified by the color change from gray to dark blue when filling in the text boxes. The login before modifications can be seen in Figure 6. The changes are presented in Figures 7 and 8.

Fig. 6. Login before corrections.

Fig. 7. Updates to link colors and "Entrar" button disabled.

When clicking on forgot password, a pop-up now opens asking for the user's email. The reset password button, which previously did not follow the style

The image shows a login form titled "Entrar" on a blue background. It contains two input fields: the first contains the email address "usuarioteste@teste.com" and the second contains a masked password "*****". Below the password field is a link "Esqueceu a senha?". At the bottom, there is a dark blue button labeled "Entrar" which is active, and a link "Ainda não tem conta? Se cadastre." below it.

Fig. 8. Button active when inserting data in text fields.

of the other buttons on the site, was standardized to maintain consistency. Modification present in Figure 10. The button before modifications can be seen in Figure 9.

The image shows two identical password reset forms titled "Redefinição de senha". Each form has a label "Informe o e-mail*" and an input field containing "Informe o e-mail". Below the input field is a button labeled "Redefir senha". In the bottom form, a mouse cursor is pointing at the button, which appears to be disabled.

Fig. 9. Password reset pop-up before modifications.

For the registration screen, links with low contrast were also changed. The text about terms of use, privacy policy, and cookies, which previously had parts in Portuguese and parts in English, is now completely in Portuguese, facilitating its understanding for users who do not understand the English language. As on the login screen, the "Cadastre-se" (Register) button remains disabled until all fields are filled. These modifications are seen in Figure 12. When clicking the button, a data confirmation pop-up was implemented so that the user can review their data and avoid sending incorrect information (Figure 13). The registration screen before modifications can be seen in Figure 11.

Fig. 10. Password reset pop-up with standardized reset button.

Fig. 11. Registration before modifications.

Cadastro-se

Informe seu e-mail

Informe seu nome e sobrenome

Informe uma senha

Repita sua senha

Escreva novamente a senha, para confirmação.

Quero receber boletim informativo

Cadastro se

Já possui conta? [Entrar](#).

Ao clicar em Registrar, você aceita nossos [Termos de Uso](#), e [Política de Privacidade](#), bem como o uso de cookies.

Fig. 12. Correction of link contrast, translation of texts that were in English, and "Cadastro-se" button enabled only when filling in the fields.

Cadastro-se

Confirmar Dados

Você está prestes a criar uma conta vinculada ao e-mail `usuarioteste@teste.com`.

Por favor, verifique se o e-mail está correto. Enviaremos uma confirmação para ele.

[Cancelar](#) [Cadastrar](#)

Já possui conta? [Entrar](#).

Ao clicar em Registrar, você aceita nossos [Termos de Uso](#), e [Política de Privacidade](#), bem como o uso de cookies.

Fig. 13. Registration data confirmation pop-up.

The problem present on the home screen was the existence of duplicated buttons, which added unnecessary elements to the interface and could confuse the user. As a correction, the buttons present in Figure 14 were kept, while the buttons present in Figure 15 were removed.

Fig. 14. Buttons maintained on the home screen.

Fig. 15. Duplicated buttons removed from the home screen.

On the "Organizações" (currently "Instituições") cards, the problem of long texts summarizing the institutions had been found, resulting in an excess of information that could harm readability and navigation on this screen. It was decided to remove these texts, as the institutions' names themselves already provide a brief idea regarding their purposes and areas of activity. The cards before modification can be seen in Figure 16. The modification can be seen in Figure 17.

The titles present in the search tabs were standardized regarding capitalization. The titles now follow the pattern where both words, all in lowercase, except for the first letter of each word, which is capitalized. The color of the "Busca" (Search) text was also corrected to the blue present in the site's theme. The title before changes can be seen in Figure 18. The modifications can be seen in Figure 19.

On the invalid link page, the color of the "Voltar para a home" (Back to home) button, which was pink, was corrected to blue, ensuring system consistency and standardization. The button was renamed to "Voltar para o início" (Back to start) to facilitate understanding by users who do not have knowledge of the English language. The button before modifications can be seen in Figure 20. Update presented in Figure 21.

Fig. 16. Cards with the presence of long texts.

Fig. 17. Cards now display only the Institution's name.

busca Iniciativa

Fig. 18. Titles of the search tabs before changes.

Buscar Instituições

Fig. 19. The titles follow the pattern where only the first letter of each word is capitalized, keeping the rest in lowercase.

O link de ativação é inválido!

Fig. 20. "Voltar para a home" button before modifications.

In addition to the visual modifications presented, the problem with the link to the news page, in the footer, which did not work correctly and sent the user to the 404 error page (page not found), was corrected. After the correction, the link now directs the user to the news page.

O link de ativação é inválido!

Fig. 21. "Voltar para o início" button corrected to blue.

Further checks can be performed during user login and registration, such as the problem of the lack of a dynamic alert indicating password difference during registration. With Figma, this functionality cannot be implemented in the prototype and should therefore be included directly in the code as future work.

Regarding the complete translation of the screens into English and Spanish, it was also not possible to implement it in the Figma prototype because it does not have a native function for this, making it necessary to duplicate each screen to translate manually. As this change would take too much time, it was decided not to translate and leave this task as future work, to be implemented directly in the code, given that the usability test applied to the prototype would have Portuguese-speaking participants as its scope.